

Mass Spectral Studies on Alkyltin (IV) Oxinates*

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Bis(5-nitro-8-quinolinolato)dimethyltin(IV), bis(5-nitro-8-quinolinolato)diethyltin(IV), bis(5-nitro-8-quinolinolato)dibutyltin(IV), bis(5,7-dichloro-8-quinolinolato)diethyltin(IV) and bis(5,7-dichloro-8-quinolinolato)dibutyltin(IV) are isolated in pure condition. The mass spectra of these compounds along with dialkyltin(IV) chelates with 8-quinolinol are reported. Parent ions are either low abundant or absent in the spectra of all these compounds and the fragmentation of the molecular ion by elimination of an alkyl or a ligand radical is a major mode of dissociation. In all the dialkyltin(IV) chelates, lower metal valency ions occur abundantly. The mass spectra of several 5- and 7-substituted and 5, 7-disubstituted 8-quinolinols are also reported. The fragmentation pathways based upon interpretation of spectra and meta stable transitions are discussed.

ALTHOUGH the application of mass spectrometry to the characterization of organotin compounds is steadily increasing, the reported investigations mostly deal with organotin derivatives, such as, tin tetraalkyls¹⁻⁵ or aryls^{6,7}, alkyl or aryltin(IV) halides^{8,9} mixed alkyl-aryl tin compounds⁶ and organometallic compounds containing Sn-metal (Group IV) bond¹⁰. Mass spectral studies on alkyltin chelates, however, have received scant attention. As a part of a general study on organotin compounds, we have investigated the behaviour, under electron impact, of some alkyltin chelates with 8-quinolinol and substituted 8-quinolinols along with 5- and 7-substituted and 5-7-disubstituted 8-quinolinols which are not reported earlier and the results of our studies are presented here. Alkyltin oxinates are chosen for our investigations because of their stability and convenient volatility.

Experimental

The mass spectra of the compounds were recorded on CEC 41-110B (USA) double focusing mass spectrometer at a voltage of 70 eV and a current of 20 milliamperes.

Diethylindichloride was prepared according to the method described by Luijten and Vander Kerk¹¹ and was purified by several recrystallisations from petroleum ether (40°-60°). m.p., 83.5° (reported¹¹ 83°-84°). Found : Sn, 47.14 ; Cl, 28.25%. Calc. for C₄H₁₀SnCl₂ : Sn, 47.9 ; Cl, 28.7%. Dimethylindichloride was purified by sublimation prior to use. Dibutylindichloride (of Estman Organic Chemicals) was used as such.

5, 7-Disubstituted and 5-, and 7-substituted-8-quinolinols were prepared according to the literature methods. These compounds were purified by repeated crystallisations from solvents.

5-Nitro-8-quinolinol : m.p., 178° (reported¹², m.p. 178°). Found : C, 57.11 ; H, 2.86%. Calc. for C₉H₆N₂O₃ : C, 56.83 ; H, 2.65%.

7-Nitro-8-quinolinol : m.p., 168°-70° (165°-66°)¹³. Found : C, 57.37 ; H, 3.47%. Calc. for C₉H₆N₂O₃ : C, 56.83 ; H, 2.65%.

5,7-Dinitro-8-quinolinol : m.p., 319-20° (318°)¹⁴. Found : C, 46.49 ; H, 1.94%. Calc. for C₉H₅N₃O₅ : C, 45.95 ; H, 1.71%.

5 Nitro, 7-bromo-8-quinolinol : m.p., 202° (200°)¹². Found : C, 41.19 ; H, 2.90%. Calc. for C₉H₅N₂O₃Br : C, 40.30 ; H, 1.96%.

7-Nitro, 5-bromo-8-quinolinol : m.p., 195°-6° (195°-6°)¹⁵. Found : C, 39.51 ; H, 1.98%. Calc. for C₉H₅N₂O₃Br : C, 40.30 ; H, 1.86%.

5, 7-Dichloro-8-quinolinol : m.p., 179°-80° (178°-9°)¹⁶. Found : C, 50.47 ; H, 2.33%. Calc. for C₉H₅NOCl₂ : C, 50.15 ; H, 2.04%.

5, 7-Dibromo-8-quinolinol : m.p., 195°-6° (195°-6°)¹⁷. Found : C, 36.31 ; H, 2.13%. Calc. for C₉H₅NOBr₂ : C, 35.65 ; H, 1.65%.

5, 7-Diiodo-8-quinolinol : m.p., 214° (214°-15°)¹⁸. Found : C, 27.88 ; H, 1.50%. Calc. for C₉H₅NOI₂ : C, 27.20 ; H, 1.26%.

Bis(8-quinolinolato)dimethyltin (IV), bis(8-quinolinolato)diethyltin(IV), and bis(8-quinolinolato)dibutyltin (IV) were prepared by the method described by Tanaka *et al*¹⁹. by treating the alcoholic solutions of dialkyltin-dichlorides with 8-quinolinol in 1 : 2 mole proportions followed by the addition of dilute ammonia. The fine yellow crystalline precipitates obtained were purified from petroleum ether (40°-60°).

Bis(8-quinolinolato)dioctyltin (IV) was obtained in increased yield by slightly modifying the general procedure described for the preparation of diphenyl- and dibutyltin complexes with 8-quinolinol by Blake *et al*²⁰. The starting material was dioctyltin oxide instead of the dioctyltin dichloride. Solutions of dioctyltin oxide (1.81 g ; 0.005 mole) in DMF (15 ml) and 8-quinolinol (1.45 g ; 0.01 mole) in DMF (30-35 ml) were mixed together and refluxed for 2 hr., and the product was precipitated by the addition of sodium acetate solution (1.2 g ; in 15 ml). The yellow crystalline solid was collected on a filter and dried. Yield, 2.7 g. (85.92%). It was recrystallised from petroleum ether, m.p., 78° (78°)²¹. Found : C, 65.48 ; H, 7.65 ; N, 4.84 ; Sn, 17.64%. Calc. for C₃₄H₄₆N₂O₂Sn : C, 64.56 ; H, 7.28 ; N, 4.43 ; S, 18.78%.

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Bis(5-nitro-8-quinolinolato), dimethyltin(IV) Dime-
thyltin dichloride (1.0 g; 0.005 mole) in alcohol
(10 ml) and 5-nitro-8-quinolinol (1.0g, 0.01 mole) in hot
alcohol (100 ml) were mixed together. Dilute ammonia
(1 : 1) was added to the mixture with stirring and the
precipitated lemon yellow complex was collected in a
filter under suction, washed with alcohol (5 ml) and
dried. Yield, 2.15 g (98.6%).

It was recrystallised from benzene. m.p., 280°-1°.
Found : C, 46.30; H, 3.36; N, 11.21; Sn, 23.0%. Calc.
for C₂₀H₁₆N₄O₆Sn : C, 45.53; H, 3.05; N, 10.63;
Sn, 22.53%.

Bis(5-nitro-8-quinolinolato)diethyltin(IV) : Diethyl-
tin dichloride (1.12 g; 0.005 mole) in alcohol
(10 ml) and 5-nitro-8-quinolinol (1.90 g; 0.01 mole) in
alcohol (100 ml) were mixed together and the compound
was obtained by the addition, with stirring, of an
aqueous solution of sodium acetate (1.2 g. in 15 ml)
followed by ammonia (1 : 1) Yield, 2.3 g. (82.9%). It
was purified by crystallisation from benzene. m.p.,
210°-2°. Found : C, 48.9; H, 3.8; N, 9.91; Sn, 21.13%.
Calc. for C₂₂H₂₀N₄O₆Sn : C, 47.62; H, 3.63;
N, 10.09; Sn, 21.38%.

Bis(5-nitro-8-quinolinolato) dibutyltin(IV) : This
compound was prepared by following essentially the
same procedure for bis (5-nitro-8-quinolinolato) diethyl-
tin (IV). The only modification was, after mixing,
solutions of dibutyltin dichloride (1.5 g; 0.005 mole) in
alcohol (10 ml) and 5-nitro-8-quinolinol (1.98 g, 0.01
mole) in alcohol (100 ml), the mixture was refluxed for
2 hr. Yield, 1.5 g. (50%). Recrystallised from benzene,
m.p., 229-30°C. Found : C, 51.45; H, 4.9; N, 8.9;
Sn, 20.03%. Calc. for C₂₆H₂₈N₄O₆Sn : C, 51.15;
H, 4.52; N, 9.17; Sn, 19.43%.

Bis(5,7-dichloro-8-quinolinolato)diethyltin(IV) :
Diethyltin-dichloride (0.6 g; 0.0025 mole) in alcohol
(10 ml) and 5,7-dichloro-8-quinolinol (1.07 g, 0.005
mole) in hot alcohol (50 ml) containing a few drops of
acetic acid were mixed together. The mixture was
heated for 5-10 min. on a hot plate. The yellow solid
obtained on cooling was collected on a filter, dried and
recrystallised from benzene. Yield, 1.2 g. (80%), m.p.,
144°-5°. Found : C, 43.62; H, 2.99; Cl, 22.70; Sn,
19.11%. Calc. for C₂₂H₁₈N₂O₂Cl₄ Sn : C, 43.80;
H, 2.99; Cl, 22.70; Sn, 19.70%.

Bis(5,7-dichloro-8-quinolinolato)dibutyltin(IV)
This compound was obtained by mixing solutions of
dibutyltin dichloride (0.5 g, 0.0025 mole) in alcohol
(10 ml) and 5,7-dichloro-8-quinolinol (1.6g, 0.005 mole)
in hot alcohol (50 ml) containing a few drops of acetic
acid and by following the experimental procedure de-
scribed for bis (5,7-dichloro-8-quinolinolato) diethyl-
tin (IV). Yield, 1.5 g. (90.8%). m.p., 144-5° Found :
C, 47.13; H, 4.15; Cl, 22.06; Sn, 17.89%. Calc. for
C₂₆H₂₆N₂O₂Cl₄ Sn : C, 47.42; H, 3.95; Cl, 21.28;
Sn, 18.03%.

Results and Discussion

The mass spectra of 5-nitro-8-quinolinol (II), 7-nitro-
8-quinolinol (III), 5,7-dinitro-8-quinolinol (IV), 5-nitro-
7-bromo-8-quinolinol (V), 5-bromo-7-nitro-8-quinolinol
(VI), 5,7-dichloro-8-quinolinol (VII), 5,7-dibromo-
8-quinolinol (VIII) and 5,7-diiodo-8-quinolinol (IX)
have been recorded along with alkyltin complexes with
I, II and VII. The mass spectrum of 8-quinolinol (I) is
previously reported by Clugston and Maclean^{2,2}.

In the mass spectra of all the 5- and 7-substituted
and 5,7-disubstituted 8-quinolinols, the molecular ion
is the strongest peak except in compounds V and VI.
The spectra of substituted 8-quinolinols may be divided
into two groups on the basis of intensities of peaks of
the fragment ions. The first group composed of 5-nitro-
7-nitro-, 5,7-dinitro-, 5-nitro-7-bromo and 5-bromo-
7-nitro 8-quinolinols exhibit (Table 1) relatively strong
peaks for the fragment ions corresponding to the loss
of NO (loss of 30 mass units) followed by the loss of
28 mass units (CO) from the molecular ion. Expulsion
of the substituent group(s) accompanied by the loss of
CO from the molecular ion is also observed. The second
group (Table 2) composed of 5,7-dichloro-, 5,7-
dibromo- and 5,7-diiodo-8-quinolinols exhibit facile loss
of CO as well as loss of CO preceded by the loss of
H (1 mass unit). [(M-29)⁺, meta stable supported] at
reduced intensities. The main spectral features of this
group are similar to those of 8-quinolinol. Clugston
and Maclean^{2,2} have discussed the main features of the
mass spectra of monohydroxy substituted quinolines,
viz. loss of CO from the molecular ion, followed by the

TABLE 1—MASS SPECTRAL DATA FOR 5-,7- AND 5,7-SUBSTITUTED
8-QUINOLINOLS WITH THE GENERAL FORMULA*: RELATIVE
ABUNDANCE (%) OF THE PRINCIPAL ION SPECIES OBSERVED
IN THE SPECTRA OF COMPOUNDS II-VI

Principal ion	II	III	IV	V	VI
[M] ⁺	100	100	100	62.7	64.7
[M-X]	12.06	—	8.1	13.3	—
[M-Y]	—	10.4	—	—	6.1
[M-X-Y]	—	—	26.5	1.3	14.2
[M-X-CO]	41.2	—	—	18.7	—
[M-Y-CO]	—	75.9	—	—	36.4
[M-X-Y-CO]	—	—	75.5	100	100
[M-X-Y-CO-HCN]	—	—	30.6	40.0	38.4
[M-NO]	41.8	27.6	28.6	28.0	17.2
[M-NO-NO ₂]	—	—	10.2	—	—
[M-NO-NO ₂ -O]	—	—	14.3	—	—
[M-NO-NO ₂ -O-CO]	—	—	71.4	—	—
[M-NO-CO]	2.9	48.3	—	1.3	23.2
[M-X or Y-CO-HCN]	25.4	48.3	—	—	—
[M-NO-CO-X or Y]	—	—	—	2.7	2.0
[M-O]	—	—	4.1	—	—

II. X=NO₂; Y=H
III. X=H; Y=NO₂
IV. X=Y=NO₂
V. X=NO₂; Y=Br
VI. X=Br; Y=NO₂

TABLE 2—MASS SPECTRAL DATA FOR THE SUBSTITUTED 8-QUINOLINOLS⁺: RELATIVE ABUNDANCE (%) OF PRINCIPAL ION SPECIES OBSERVED IN THE SPECTRA OF COMPOUNDS I, VII, VIII AND IX

Principal ion*	I	VII	VIII	IX
[M] ⁺	73.2	100	53.1	33.9
[M-H]	0.9	2.2	<1	—
[M-H-CO]	16.1	6.7	1.6	1.6
[M-H-CO-HCN]	23.2	2.2	<1.0	—
[M-H-CO-X]	—	6.6	6.3	6.4
[M-H-CO-X-Y]	—	13.3	—	—
[M-H-CO-X-Y-HCN]	—	2.2	—	—
[M-X or Y]	—	2.2	—	17.8
[M-X-Y]	—	—	9.4	23.1
[M-X-Y-HCN]	—	—	4.7	12.9
[M-CO]	100	13.3	7.8	6.5
[M-CO-HCN]	19.6	—	—	—
[M-CO-X or Y]	—	22.2	42.4	61.4
[M-CO-X-Y]	—	6.6	9.4	93.5
[M-CO-X-Y-HCN]	—	2.2	3.1	37.1

* I. X=Y=H.

VII. X-Y=Cl (for comparison the relative abun-

VIII. X=Y=Br danc. (%) of the principal ions of

IX. X=Y=I 8-quinolinol are also included).

* The intensities reported are for ions containing ⁷⁹Br and ³⁵Cl.

loss of HCN and further decomposition of the resulting hydrocarbon ion. The facile loss of CO was explained on the basis of carbonium ion formation²⁸ in the phenolic ring and thus primary decomposition should involve the loss of CO from the phenoxy cation. The preferential fragmentation of the phenolic ring is followed by the fragmentation of the pyridine ring. In addition to the reported fragmentation pathways, we have observed in 8-quinolinol, some ions originating from the (M-H) ion. Although the (M-H)⁺ ion, as such is weak, m/e 116 ion which results from the expulsion of CO from this ion is fairly intense (16.1%). A meta stable peak is also observed (m/e 93.5) corresponding to this transition. Loss of HCN from m/e 116 ion leads to the ion m/e 89. Meta stable data indicate that the m/e 89 is formed from m/e 116 ion as well as m/e 90.

The mass spectral features of 5-nitro-,7-nitro and 5,7-dinitro-8-quinolinols are similar in that the major fragment ions, under electron impact, in each case are those which arise from the loss of NO or from an initial loss of NO₂ followed by CO. The spectra show strong peaks corresponding to [M-NO]⁺ and [M-NO-CO]⁺ ions. The loss of NO₂ and CO from the parent ion is followed by the expulsion of the neutral fragment HCN. This fragment ion [M-NO₂-CO-HCN]⁺, is observed as an intense peak in compounds II and III. Weak peaks which may arise due to the loss of one or both substituents in the spectra of the compounds II-VI are observed. The [M-1]⁺ ion is, however, absent in the nitro substituted-8-quinolinols. In the mass spectra of 5-nitro-7-bromo- and 7-nitro-5-bromo-8-quinolinols, the fragment ion [M-X-Y-CO]⁺, m/e 115 is the most intense. However, the (M-NO)⁺ peak is more predominant in 5-nitro-7-bromo-8-quinolinol than in 7-nitro-5-bromo-8-quinolinol. The difference in the competing frag-

mentation pathway may arise due to the position of different substituents in the aromatic ring. In their study on the mass spectra of a series of 2-substituted-8-quinolinols Stevenson *et al.*²⁸ observed that different functional groups were found to change the relative importance of competing fragmentation pathways of the compounds.

In the mass spectra of the alkyltin (IV) chelates with 8-quinolinol and 5-nitro- and 5, 7-dichloro-8-quinolinols, parent molecular ions are either low abundant or absent and the fragments involving the loss of an alkyl radical or ligand are quite abundant. The salient feature commonly observed in the spectra of all the tin complexes is the fragmentation of the molecular ion resulting in species of lower valency state in abundance, by elimination of either a ligand or an alkyl radical or both alkyl radicals along with a ligand.

The base peak in the spectrum of bis(8-quinolinolato)-dimethyltin (IV) observed, is the ion SnL⁺, at m/e 264 formed according to Scheme I and the molecular ion is of low abundance (1.3%). The first reaction, upon electron impact, involving the loss of a CH₃ radical from the molecular ion is shown by the ion m/e 423. The reaction appears to resemble the formation of MR₃⁺ ions of high abundance in tin tetra alkyls and related compounds^{6,24-28}. The loss of the methyl radical is followed by loss of another CH₃ radical, forming lower valency state ion, [Sn(L)₂]⁺ at m/e 408. This is supported by the presence of a meta stable peak at m/e 393.5. Further elimination of a ligand radical results in the formation of ion of another lower valency state, Sn⁺(L) (m/e 264). The relative abundance of the peak suggests that the species ¹¹⁹Sn⁺L has high stability. It has been recently demonstrated that the valencies of the metal atoms can alter during ion reactions and the valency changes may be an important factor contributing to the driving force of such reactions²⁹⁻³². Ocolowitz²⁸ in his study on electron impact fragmentation of some organotin compounds observed that the fragmentation process giving a new radical ion with a lower metal valency appears to occur preferentially in coordination compounds. In covalent tin compounds the species ¹¹⁹Sn⁺R₃, (¹¹⁹SnR₂)⁺, ¹¹⁹Sn⁺R occur abundantly.

Another prominent mode of decomposition involves the direct loss of the ligand from the parent molecular ion (m/e 294). During the course of the ionization

TABLE 3—RELATIVE ABUNDANCE (%) OF PRINCIPAL ION SPECIES OBSERVED IN THE MASS SPECTRA OF ALKYL TIN (IV) CHELATES.

Ions*	(CH ₃) ₂ Sn(L) ₂	(C ₂ H ₅) ₂ Sn(L) ₂	(C ₄ H ₉) ₂ Sn(L) ₂	(C ₈ H ₁₇) ₂ Sn(L) ₂
[M] ⁺	1.3	—	—	—
[M-R]	43.4	34.8	76.1	35.0
[M-2R]	1.3	2.3	14.1	8.3
[M-L]	39.5	6.7	9.0	8.3
[M-2R-L]	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0
[L-H]	9.2	15.7	33.3	81.6
[L]	10.5	6.7	10.0	2.1
m/e 117	7.9	15.73	32.9	68.7
m/e 116	34.2	28.1	31.62	16.6
m/e 90	6.6	7.3	19.7	20.1
m/e 89	22.37	16.9	38.0	25.5

L=8-Quinololato ion, OX⁻
R=alkyl

* The intensities reported are for the ion containing ¹²⁰Sn.

reactions, the ions, m/e 145 (OXH)⁺ and m/e 144 (ligand-H⁺) are formed and these further undergo meta stable-supported transformations giving the ions m/e 117, m/e 116, m/e 90 and m/e 89 as shown in Schemes I and IV. In the series of alkyltin complexes with 8-quinolinol examined, it is observed that with increasing chain length in the alkyl group, the relative abundance of the peak at m/e 145 increased while that of the ion m/e 144 generally decreased (Table 3). This may be due to the fact that when the alkyl groups are larger, the hydrogen transfer to the ligand radical is accomplished with ease.

The peak at m/e 158 observed in the spectra of dimethyl- and diethyl bis(8-quinolinolato)tin(IV)chelates, can be explained on the basis of a skeletal rearrangement as shown in Schemes II and III. Several such skeletal rearrangement processes accompanied by bond cleavage are reported^{3,3}.

In the spectra of all the tin chelates metal containing fragment ion appears as a series of peaks close to each other as tin has several naturally occurring isotopes.

In the mass spectrum of bis(8-quinolinolato)diethyl tin (IV), the molecular ion is not observed and the peak corresponding to the ion, Sn⁺(L) is the strongest. This ion is formed by the loss successively of the two ethyl radicals (m/e 437 and m/e 408) and a ligand radical according to the scheme IV. Another mode of decomposition observed in the spectrum, apart from the loss of a ligand molecule directly from the molecular ion, is the loss of a CH₃ radical accompanied by ethylene elimination (m/e 423) (Scheme IV). The elimination of ethylene in tetraethyltin and other ethyl tin compounds is previously reported by Chambers *et al*⁶.

The decomposition patterns of dibutyl and dioctyl bis(8-quinolinolato)tin(IV) chelates are similar to that of the dimethyltin chelate.

In the mass spectra of dimethyl-, diethyl and dibutyl bis(5-nitro-8-quinolinolato)tin (IV) chelates, the fragments corresponding to elimination of a ligand or an alkyl radical are the most abundant and molecular ions are low abundant or absent. The first reaction, under the ionization process, in the spectrum of bis(5-nitro-8-quinolinolato)dimethyltin (IV) involving the loss of a methyl radical from the molecular ion is shown by the ion at m/e 513. (Scheme V). Meta-stable-confirmed loss of another CH₃ radical results in the formation of a lower valency state ion, [Sn(L₁)₂]⁺ (m/e 49⁺). Further fragmentation involving the elimination of a ligand takes place, giving rise to the ion, Sn⁺L₁ (m/e 309). The direct loss of a ligand radical from the molecular ion is observed at m/e 339, the formation of the ligand, [L₁H]⁺ during the ionization process is also observed (m/e 190). The relative abundance of m/e 190 in dimethyl-diethyl- and dibutyl-bis(5-nitro-8-quinolinolato)-tin(IV) compounds increased, while that of the ion m/e 189 decreased with increasing chain length in

the alkyl group (Table IV). The decomposition patterns of diethyl- and dibutyl-bis-(5-nitro-8-quinolinolato) tin (IV) compounds are similar to the methyl tin chelate.

In the mass spectra of diethyl- and dibutyl (bis (5, 7-dichloro-8-quinolinolato)tin (IV) complexes, very weak molecular ion peaks are observed. The peaks corresponding to the ion $\text{Sn}(\text{L}_2)^+$, however, are the most abundant. The ions at m/e 390 and at m/e 573 in the spectrum of diethyl bis-(5, 7-dichloro-8-quinolinolato) tin (IV), correspond to the elimination of a ligand radical or an alkyl group respectively. The corresponding ions in the dibutyl tin chelate are observed at m/e 446 and at m/e 601 respectively. The other principal fragmentation mechanism in these compounds is similar to the other dialkyl tin chelates with 8-quinolinol or 5-nitro-8-quinolinol.

TABLE 4—RELATIVE ABUNDANCE (%) OF PRINCIPAL ION SPECIES OBSERVED IN THE MASS SPECTRA OF ALKYL TIN(IV) CHELATES

Ions	$(\text{CH}_3)_2$ $\text{Sn}(\text{L}_1)_2^*$	$(\text{C}_2\text{H}_5)_2$ $\text{Sn}(\text{L}_1)_2$	$(\text{C}_4\text{H}_9)_2$ $\text{Sn}(\text{L}_1)_2$	$(\text{C}_2\text{H}_5)_2$ $\text{Sn}(\text{L}_2)_2^*$	$(\text{C}_4\text{H}_9)_2$ $\text{Sn}(\text{L}_2)_2$
$[\text{M}]^{\dagger}$	—	2.3	—	—	<0.5
$[\text{M}-\text{R}]$	82.3	69.8	24.1	32.48	14.65
$[\text{M}-2\text{R}]$	26.2	4.7	2.1	<1.0	4.9
$[\text{M}-\text{L}_1 \text{ or } \text{L}_2]$	76.8	100	14.3	18.14	28.2
$[\text{M}-2\text{R}-\text{L}_1 \text{ or } \text{L}_2]$	71.7	52.4	100	96.4	100.0
$[\text{L}_1\text{H} \text{ or } \text{L}_2\text{H}]$	41.8	52.2	75.5	13.4	25.2
$[\text{L}_1 \text{ or } \text{L}_2]$	7.2	2.4	2.0	5.9	1.94
$[\text{L}_1\text{H}-\text{NO}]$	40.8	61.9	69.4	—	—
$[\text{L}_1\text{H}-\text{NO}-\text{CO}]$	30.8	9.3	6.1	—	—
$[\text{L}_2\text{H}-\text{CO}]$	—	—	—	4.64	4.85
$[\text{L}_2\text{H}-\text{CO}-\text{Cl}]$	—	—	—	8.8	8.7

* $\text{L}_1 = 5\text{-nitro-8-quinolinolato ion } 5\text{-nitro OX}^-$
 * $\text{L}_2 = 5,7\text{-dichloro-8-quinolinolato ion } 5,7\text{-dichloro OX}^-$
 R = alkyl

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